

Trial Protocol

The C*STEROID Feasibility Study: Corticosteroids before planned caesarean section from 35⁺⁰ to 39⁺⁶ weeks

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List of abbreviations

AE	Adverse Event
ALPS	Antenatal Betamethasone for Women at Risk for Late Preterm Delivery
CRF	Case Report Form
CS	Caesarean Section
DMC	Data Monitoring Committee
GA	Gestational Age
IQ	Intelligence Quotient
HRC	Health Research Council
MFM	Maternal Fetal Medicine
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
NNU	Neonatal Unit
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RDS	Respiratory Distress Syndrome
RR	Relative risk
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
SAR	Serious Adverse Reaction
SUSAR	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction
TSC	Trial Steering Committee
TTN	Transient tachypnoea of the newborn

1. LAY SUMMARY

In New Zealand, around 7000 babies are born by planned caesarean section (CS) each year and rates continue to rise. Planned CS poses some risk to babies, in particular, the need for admission to the neonatal unit (NNU) for breathing support which means mothers are separated from their baby.

When given to mothers expecting a preterm birth, corticosteroid injections save babies' lives and improve neonatal and childhood health. This knowledge has led clinicians to prescribe corticosteroids before a planned CS at or near term. Limited research in this area has shown that as well as benefits on neonatal breathing corticosteroids may increase neonatal hypoglycaemia and so possibly cause harm. The C*STEROID Feasibility Study will take place in two maternity units over a 12 month period to inform the recruitment strategy and trial processes of the planned, national C*STEROID Trial. Results of the C*STEROID Feasibility Study will contribute to the C*STEROID Trial.

The C*STEROID Trial will be a New Zealand-wide, placebo-controlled, randomised trial to assess the effects of corticosteroids given to the mother prior to a planned CS at or near term on neonatal and later childhood health.

2. BACKGROUND

The rate of birth by planned, also referred to as elective and pre-labour, CS continues to rise each year and now accounts for more than one in ten births and almost 7000 babies born in New Zealand each year (Figure 1).¹ Compared to vaginal birth, CS poses additional risks to baby. Most specifically respiratory morbidity, often referred to as respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and transient tachypnoea of the newborn (TTN). Term and late preterm babies rarely die from this, but the need for respiratory support requires neonatal unit (NNU) admission and separates mother and baby.

Figure 1. Rates of CS in New Zealand 2005-2015.¹

Figure 2. Neonatal respiratory morbidity after elective CS compared to intended vaginal birth (reference) by gestational age.²

Gestational Age	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% CI
37 weeks	3.7	2.2-6.1
38 weeks	3.0	2.1-4.4
39 weeks	1.9	1.2-3.0
40 weeks	0.9	0.2-3.7

Neonatal respiratory morbidity after birth by pre-labour planned CS is increased 7-fold compared with infants born vaginally and 3-fold compared with infants born by CS once labour has established.^{3,4} Gestational age at birth also contributes to this increased risk; ^{2,5} hence, national practice guidelines recommend planned CS should occur $\geq 39^{+0}$ weeks.⁶⁻⁸ However, planned CS at late preterm or early term gestation may still be necessary on maternal and/or fetal grounds, and planned CS at 39^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks still imposes a 2-fold increase in neonatal respiratory morbidity.²

Maternal administration of corticosteroids prior to preterm birth at $<35^{+0}$ weeks gestation provides protection against RDS, perinatal death and neonatal adverse outcomes with little or no evidence of later harm.^{8,9} **What is less clear is if their use at gestational ages ≥ 35 weeks, and specifically prior to planned CS, provides benefit without harm.**

Evidence from randomised trials is limited. A 2016 systematic review and meta-analysis identified six trials of antenatal corticosteroids ≥ 35 weeks but only three were specific to planned CS ($\geq 37^{+0}$ weeks).¹⁰ This review demonstrated benefit, at least in the short term with a reduction in RDS (5.5% vs 7.2%, RR 0.7 95%CI 0.6-0.9) and TTN (5.9% vs 9.1%, RR 0.6 95%CI 0.4-0.9) with corticosteroid use. However, recent commentaries highlight the potential for harm,¹¹⁻¹³ supported by an unanticipated finding of the Antenatal Betamethasone for Women at Risk for Late Preterm Delivery (ALPS) trial. This is the largest trial to date, including 2827 women at high risk of imminent birth at 34^{+0} - 36^{+6} weeks¹⁴, and although respiratory morbidity was significantly reduced, the rates of neonatal hypoglycaemia were significantly higher in babies exposed to corticosteroids (22.8% vs 14.2%, RR 1.6 95% CI 1.4-1.9). Neonatal hypoglycaemia has been demonstrated to be the only common neonatal morbidity in moderate preterm children to be associated with developmental delay¹⁵ and has been associated with a dose-dependent increase in risk of poor executive function and visual motor function at four years of age in a cohort of moderate to late preterm and term infants.¹⁶ Thus the finding in the ALPS trial is a major concern which requires further consideration and evaluation.

The risk of neonatal hypoglycaemia after corticosteroids prior to planned CS birth $\geq 37^{+0}$ weeks is unknown as none of the randomised trials to date have reported rates of hypoglycaemia.¹⁰ There are no high quality data on later benefit or harm associated with term and late preterm use of corticosteroids. Only one trial with limited follow-up (37%) has reported childhood outcomes after corticosteroids prior to planned CS $\geq 37^{+0}$ weeks, with a suggestion of poorer academic performance at 8-15 years of age after maternal corticosteroid use.¹⁷

Advice from national and international guidelines in this area is limited and conflicting.^{6-8,18-22} Until recently the UK RCOG guideline recommended their use for planned CS $\leq 38^{+6}$ weeks. This guideline now has been archived and its replacement gives no guidance on this common clinical dilemma.^{6,18} The ACOG recommends use for all births at 34^{+0} to 36^{+6} weeks but again no advice is given for planned CS $>36^{+6}$ weeks.¹⁹ Data from our own work show significant variation in practice across New Zealand with some units routinely offering corticosteroids prior to all planned CS birth $\leq 38^{+6}$ weeks,²² despite the 2015 guidelines from Australia and New Zealand concluding there is insufficient evidence to make a recommendation for planned CS $>34^{+6}$ weeks.⁸ However, these guidelines do include a research recommendation calling for randomised trials to investigate the neonatal effects and childhood disability rates when corticosteroids are administered to women prior to planned CS at term.⁸

We are working to establish The C*STEROID Trial as a large multicentre randomised placebo controlled trial with sufficient power to assess both potential beneficial (respiratory) and harmful (hypoglycaemia) effects of corticosteroids prior to planned CS at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks and from this, to establish a randomised cohort able to assess the childhood benefits and/or harm of this intervention.

In preparing for such a large undertaking we now propose the C*STEROID Feasibility Study a two-site, randomised placebo controlled trial of corticosteroids before planned CS delivery at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks of pregnancy to determine feasibility for recruitment to the main C*STEROID Trial.

3. TRIAL HYPOTHESIS & AIMS

3.1 Hypothesis

The primary hypothesis is that women will be willing to take part in a trial of antenatal corticosteroids prior to planned CS at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks.

3.2 Aims

1. To identify how many women are willing to participate in a randomised trial of corticosteroid use prior to planned CS at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks (recruitment rate).
2. To identify which groups of women are willing to participate (by indication for CS, gestational age, hospital type).
3. To identify reasons why women may decline to participate in such a trial.
4. To identify key issues that may arise for women considering trial participation and for the researchers and medical professionals involved in the trial in practice in order to inform the most effective national roll-out of the C*STEROID Trial.
5. To accurately assess the feasibility of undertaking serial measurements of neonatal pre-feed blood glucose concentrations.
6. To contribute outcome data to the full C*STEROID Trial.

4. TRIAL & DRUG SAFETY

4.1 Potential Risks to the Baby

Antenatal corticosteroids including betamethasone are used as standard practice for mothers at high risk of preterm birth at <35⁺⁰ weeks gestation to provide protection against RDS, perinatal death and other measures of neonatal adverse outcome with little or no evidence of later harm.^{9,10} Previous research suggests that it may provide protection against respiratory conditions at later gestational ages and specifically when given before planned CS. This trial will assess other risks to the baby, in particular, neonatal hypoglycaemia. To date no trials of corticosteroids prior to planned CS at term or near term gestational ages have included data on rates of neonatal hypoglycaemia or included its measurement as a standard of the protocol.

4.2 Potential Risks to the Mother

The use of maternal corticosteroids may impose risk relating to infection morbidity. This has not been seen in previous trials.^{9,10} However, to date no trials of corticosteroids prior to planned CS only at term or near term gestational ages have included data on maternal outcomes including any infection. This trial will assess and quantify maternal infection risk.

5. STUDY DESIGN

The C*STEROID Feasibility Study is a two-site, double-blind, randomised placebo controlled trial.

5.1 Trial Setting

This trial will be conducted at two maternity units: National Women's Health, Auckland City Hospital, and Tauranga Hospital. National Women's Health is a large 'research-active' tertiary unit with experience in recruiting women and babies to large multi-centre randomised trials. It has a relatively high rate of planned CS due to the number of high risk women referred to this unit through the public system as well as the number of women receiving private obstetric care and choosing a planned CS. Tauranga Hospital is a smaller secondary unit with a general maternity population and a lower rate of planned CS. It is relatively new to engagement in perinatal clinical trials.

5.2 Trial Co-ordination

The trial will be coordinated by staff at The University of Auckland including the C*STEROID Feasibility Study Principal Investigator and Lead Investigators, Clinical Trial Manager, research midwives, PhD student(s) and any other staff required to support clinical trial activities or analysis.

6. STUDY POPULATION – Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria

Women for whom CS is planned pre-labour at 35⁺⁰ to 39⁺⁶ weeks gestation at National Women’s Health, Auckland City Hospital and Tauranga Hospital.

6.1 Inclusion Criteria:

- Planned pre-labour CS $\geq 35^{+0}$ - 39⁺⁶ weeks gestation
- >24 hours* and <7 days until planned birth
- Singleton or twin pregnancy

*Randomisation will be permitted at ≥ 20 hours prior to planned birth.

6.2 Exclusion Criteria:

- Diabetes (pre-existing or gestational)*
- Non-viable fetus or major fetal abnormality
- Prior corticosteroid use in this pregnancy (intramuscular corticosteroid use for fetal lung maturity)

*Women with pre-existing or gestational diabetes will not be included in this trial as risks for neonatal respiratory morbidity and hypoglycaemia are significantly different in these populations.

6.3 Withdrawal of Participants

All study participants are free to discontinue the study drug and/or withdraw their consent at any point during treatment without prejudice. Participants who elect to discontinue the study drug early (receive no or one dose only) will continue with all other trial involvement unless they specify that they wish to withdraw from the study.

If a participant indicates that they wish to withdraw their consent for further participation data collected to the point of withdrawal will be retained and used, including as part of the C*STEROID Trial intention to treat analysis. The investigator will be encouraged to ask a participant who is withdrawing which level of continued participation they agree to, if any, and to document this in the CRF. If a participant specifically requests complete withdrawal of consent, publicly available information only such as from the Birth Register may still be accessed to collect survival status. All participants will receive on-going medical care according to clinical need.

7. STUDY NUMBERS & POWER CALCULATION

7.1 C*STEROID Feasibility Study

The number of participants recruited will be a key finding of the feasibility study. This is expected to be 200-400 women over a 12 month period.

7.2 Feasibility of Recruitment

The C*STEROID Feasibility Study aims to determine feasibility of recruitment to the planned C*STEROID Trial. This will significantly strengthen the feasibility work completed to date, which includes;

Concept Development Workshop: The C*STEROID Trial was developed at a national two day Concept Development Workshop hosted by the ON TRACK Network in February 2017. A multi-disciplinary group developed the protocol facilitated by experts in the field, clinicians, biostatisticians, consumers and a Māori research advisor.

Site Participation²³: Practitioner surveys sent to all 18 district health boards engaged with the ON TRACK Network reviewed current practice and attitudes towards corticosteroids prior to planned CS near and at term and attitudes towards participation in a randomised trial. Of 15/18 DHBs that responded this includes approximately 40 000 births annually in 16 hospitals with planned CS rates varying from 7.9% to 18.0%, accounting for over 4500 births each year. Eleven units responded that they would be willing to participate in the proposed C*STEROID trial, a further five units were uncertain. No units were unwilling to consider participation. This survey also provided information on the number of units with clinical practice guidelines with specific advice on the use of corticosteroids prior to planned CS ≥ 35 weeks (n=8); the type of corticosteroid used (betamethasone in all units); number of units with clinical practice guidelines for monitoring for neonatal hypoglycaemia (n=13) and management neonatal hypoglycaemia (n=15); how many units have previous experience of participation in multi-centre randomised trials (n=13) and how many currently have employed research staff (n=7).

Consumer participation²⁴: We have also completed a feasibility study in women booked for a planned CS at 35⁺⁰ to 39⁺⁶ weeks at Auckland City Hospital over a three month period in 2017 to explore consumer attitudes to antenatal corticosteroid administration prior to planned CS at and near to term and to assess their potential engagement in this research.

Women were provided with background information and a questionnaire. The background information considered potential risks of planned CS including infant respiratory morbidity, current evidence about the use of antenatal corticosteroids to prevent respiratory morbidity and the possible benefits and/or harms when used after 35⁺⁰ weeks and prior to planned CS. A brief overview for a future proposed randomised placebo-controlled trial was also provided. The questionnaire collected information on participant demographic, indication for and timing of planned CS and whether the risks and benefits of CS and antenatal corticosteroids had been discussed with them by their health care provider. Likert scales were used to assess levels of current interest in corticosteroid use prior to planned CS and willingness to participate in a placebo-controlled trial. Women were also asked to identify and rank the most important potential effects of antenatal corticosteroids on their infant/child and to identify the most acceptable forms of short and longer term follow-up for clinical trial purposes. University of Auckland Human Participants Ethics Committee (019460) and Auckland District Health Board governance approval (7647).

Responses from 64 women were included at a gestational age range 36⁺⁰ to 39⁺⁵ weeks. Risks of CS had been discussed with 53 (84%) women but antenatal corticosteroids had only been discussed with

five and offered to two women. Eighteen women said that they would 'probably' or 'definitely' accept antenatal corticosteroids if it were offered and 7 answered 'not at all' in their current pregnancy. Thirty-one women (51%) would 'probably', 'definitely' or were 'unsure' if they would accept use of corticosteroids in the context of randomised placebo-controlled trial and were more likely to accept randomisation at later gestational ages. Of those willing to consider participation, 87% would be willing for their baby to undergo blood sugar testing. Women identified that the most important outcomes for their baby/child were avoiding short term breathing support in the first few hours/days of life and avoiding respiratory problems such as asthma, wheeze and chest infection as they grow up. The majority of this population had planned CS $\geq 39^{+0}$ weeks (76%) and a private obstetrician as their lead maternity carer (57%), so do not necessarily reflect attitudes once the trial is undertaken more widely for all planned CS births at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks and in all types of units.

8. PARTICIPANT SELECTION & RECRUITMENT

All women booked for a planned pre-labour CS at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks gestation at the recruiting sites will be assessed for eligibility. Once women have been identified as eligible by meeting all of the inclusion criteria, and none of the exclusion criteria, they will be provided with information regarding the trial. This will be done verbally and with a written information sheet and consent form provided by clinicians and/or site trial investigators and research staff. All women will be given time for full consideration and consultation as required. Contact telephone numbers will be provided. Clinical and/or research staff will make contact with the potential recruit and if women wish to join the study the informed consent process will be completed and written, informed consent will be obtained.

Women will be invited to take part in one or both of the following:

1. C*STEROID Feasibility Study Questionnaire: a study specific questionnaire about the participant's decision to take part in, or not take part in, the clinical trial component.
2. Randomised Clinical Trial: randomised controlled trial with administration of betamethasone or placebo (including the C*STEROID Feasibility Study Questionnaire).

For women who decline to take part in the C*STEROID Feasibility Study antenatal care will continue to the same standard as for all women undergoing planned CS at 35^{+0} to 39^{+6} weeks gestation. Corticosteroids will not be available as part of this standard of care.

9. RANDOMISATION

Eligible women who have provided written, informed consent to participate in the randomised, controlled trial will be enrolled by clinicians and research staff using a web-based randomisation service operating at the Maternal & Perinatal Central Coordinating Research Hub (CCRH) hosted by the Liggins Institute, The University of Auckland.

Randomisation will be stratified for;

1. Gestational age at planned caesarean section 35^{+0} - 36^{+6} , 37^{+0} - 38^{+6} , 39^{+0} - 39^{+9} weeks
2. Recruiting site
3. Singleton or twin pregnancy

Women will be randomised in a 1:1 ratio to betamethasone:placebo. The randomisation process will assign each participant with a unique study ID number. This study ID number will be required when allocating study drug treatment pack and for recording data on the CRF. The randomisation service provides 24 hour access, 7 days per week. If a woman is found not to be eligible for the trial when her details are entered into the randomisation program the program will return a screen failure notification.

10. TREATMENT GROUPS & STUDY DRUG

10.1 Treatment Groups

Women will be randomised to one of two groups:

1. *Betamethasone*

Two doses of 11.4 mg betamethasone (Celestone Chronodose) by intramuscular injection 24 hours (+/- 4 hours) apart given within seven days of planned CS.

OR

2. *Placebo*

Two doses of visually matching placebo by intramuscular injection 24 hours (+/- 4 hours) apart given within seven days of planned CS.

Participants, medical professionals caring for women and trial investigators will remain blinded to treatment allocation until the trial is completed.

10.2 Drug Supply and Storage

Study drug will be packaged in syringes and labelled with a study drug number. Betamethasone and visually matching placebo injections (containing no betamethasone) will be prepared by a single supplier.

The Investigator at each site is responsible for study drug inventory and accountability throughout the trial. The study drug must be stored in a limited access area or locked cabinet. Storage should be in a temperature controlled area below 25°C and syringes should be protected from light.

10.3 Drug Administration and Assessment of Compliance

The study drug will be administered by intramuscular injection, to the thigh, arm or buttock, by appropriately qualified clinical or research staff at the study site. Compliance with administration will be recorded in the CRF.

10.4 Emergency Unblinding

In the event that there is an immediate need for the treating doctor to know a participant's treatment allocation to ensure patient safety it will be possible to break the randomisation code. The facility to perform emergency unblinding will be available 24 hours per day. It is recommended that the

Investigator contact the Auckland Principal Investigator to discuss the particular situation before breaking the participant's randomisation code, if possible.

11. TREATMENT DURATION/INDICATIONS TO STOP TREATMENT

11.1 Treatment Duration

Randomised participants will be given the first dose of study drug within seven days of their planned CS and a second dose 24 hours (+/- 4 hours) later. The first dose of study drug should be scheduled to allow for the administration of two doses 24 hours (+/- 4 hours) apart prior to the participants planned CS. No further doses of study drug or antenatal corticosteroids will be given, even in the event of a delayed planned CS date.

11.2 Indications to Stop Treatment

1. Significant maternal reaction to the first injection as determined by the clinician.
2. Delivery required on clinical grounds prior to scheduled second dose of study drug.
3. Maternal request.

12. DATA COLLECTION

12.1 C*STEROID Feasibility Study Questionnaire

Individuals may consent to complete the C*STEROID Feasibility Study Questionnaire without also agreeing to take part in the randomised clinical trial. Two separate questionnaires will be used, one for women who agree to take part in the questionnaire component only (and decline participation in the randomised clinical trial) and one for women who agree to take part in the full randomised clinical trial to capture the different factors that influenced their decision.

12.2 Randomised Participants

The study procedures for randomised participants are summarised in the flow chart below.

Individual Participant Trial Flow Chart

12.2.1 Baseline Data Collection

Data will be collected on current and past medical history and demographics including date of birth, ethnicity, height and weight, past obstetric history, past medical history, complications to date in current pregnancy, medication use in pregnancy, indication(s) for CS and indication for timing of CS.

12.2.2 Baseline Questionnaires

All participants will complete the following questionnaires at the time of consent:

- A study-specific feasibility questionnaire to assess the pregnancy characteristics of women willing to participate in a randomised trial of antenatal corticosteroids prior to planned CS at 35⁺⁰ to 39⁺⁶ weeks gestation and the reasons they are willing to participate.
- The SF-36 quality of life questionnaire to assess overall health and wellbeing.
- The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EDPS) to assess mental wellbeing.

12.2.3 Randomisation and Study Drug Allocation

The randomisation process will assign each participant with a study drug treatment pack number. The system will only allocate treatment pack assigned to and available at individual recruiting site. Each treatment pack contains two syringes containing 11.4 mg betamethasone or visually matching placebo. The second dose syringe will be kept securely at the recruiting site prior to second dose.

12.2.4 Study Drug Treatment

First and second doses of study drug will be administered by clinical and qualified research staff within seven days of planned CS and 24 hours (+/- 4 hours) apart. Timing and compliance will be recorded in the CRF.

At the time of the first dose women will be provided with a Clinical Trial Participant Alert Card which will include space to record any adverse effects. At the second dose visit and on admission for planned CS, the Participant Alert Card will be reviewed and women will be asked to report any adverse reactions (local or systemic). These will be recorded in the CRF.

12.2.5 Confirmation of consent after birth

After birth written confirmation of consent for the child/children to be part of the research will be obtained. This is required pursuant to section 36 of the Care of Children Act and the Ethics Approval of this study.

12.2.6. Neonatal blood glucose monitoring

Neonatal pre-feed blood glucose concentrations (BGC) will be measured at 1-2 hours of age and then 3-4 hourly until 12 hours of age unless hypoglycaemia has occurred (continue monitoring until three consecutive blood glucose concentrations have been ≥ 2.6 mM). BGC should be measured using a glucose oxidase point-of-care device, e.g. i-STAT analyser; if this is not available alternatives such as Accucheck should be used. Method of analysis will be noted with BGC recordings. If it is not possible to complete one or more of the recommended BGC this will be recorded in the CRF along with the reason why it was not carried out. Any additional clinically indicated blood glucose levels recorded in the neonatal period will be collected. We will recommend that hypoglycaemia is treated following

the ADHB Hypoglycaemia in the neonate guideline²⁵ and the national Oral Dextrose Gel guideline.²⁶ Surveillance and treatment algorithms will be supplied to sites (Appendix).

12.2.7 Concomitant Clinical Management and Co-interventions

Management of care and any additional therapies required will be provided at the discretion of the clinician/study site. Care of the woman during the antenatal period, labour and postnatal stay will be managed by the responsible obstetric and midwifery teams and care of the neonate will be the responsibility of the neonatology and midwifery teams. Relevant data regarding co-interventions and care will be recorded in the CRF.

12.2.8 Outcome data collection

Detailed data will be collected regarding delivery, maternal and neonatal outcomes from the maternal and neonatal records. Maternal outcome data will be collected until the time of primary maternal hospital discharge. Neonatal outcome data will be collected to the time of primary hospital discharge.

12.2.9 Post-partum questionnaires

Participants will be sent the following questionnaires six weeks after delivery via email (or postal hard copy if requested):

- A study-specific questionnaire to assess breastfeeding rates and assess any maternal infection after primary discharge from hospital, and to assess satisfaction with trial participation.
- The SF-36 quality of life questionnaire to assess overall health and wellbeing.
- The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EDPS) to assess mental wellbeing.

12.3 Feasibility of recruitment: health care professionals and trial site recruitment

To assess the barriers and enablers to trial participation by research staff, medical professionals and recruiting sites focus group interviews will be conducted and site screening logs will be reviewed. Focus groups will follow a semi-structured guide and will be recorded and transcribed. These focus groups will include site research staff and clinicians. We will aim to explore barriers and enablers to site set-up, clinician and consumer engagement, trial conduct processes including ability to complete administration of study drug and neonatal pre-feed blood glucose monitoring as per protocol.

13. SAFETY ASSESSMENT & MONITORING

13.1 Assessment of Adverse Events

Information will be collected regarding all adverse events (AE) that occur from the time of randomisation until maternal and neonatal primary hospital discharge after delivery. Any events

reported in the six week post-partum questionnaire will be reviewed by the investigator for their potential to fulfil adverse event criteria and reported if necessary.

The general definition of an AE is any unfavourable and unintended change in structure, function, or chemistry of the body temporally associated with the study drug whether or not considered related to the use of the study medication. Worsening of a pre-existing condition which is temporally associated with the use of the study medication may also be considered an AE.

13.2 Serious Adverse Events

In this trial the following will be considered serious adverse events:

- Maternal death
- Fetal death
- Neonatal death
- Maternal life threatening event
- Maternal persistent or significant disability or incapacity
- Major antepartum or postpartum haemorrhage (>1500 mL)
- Other medically important event considered to be an SAE by Investigator

Important medical events that may not result in death, threat to life, or not require hospitalisation may be also considered an SAE when, based upon appropriate medical judgment, the event may jeopardise the participant and may require medical or surgical intervention to prevent one of the outcomes listed above. The term life threatening here refers to an event in which the patient is at risk of death at the time of the event; it does not refer to an event that might hypothetically cause death if it was more severe.

13.3 Investigator Review of AEs/SAEs:

The maximum intensity of adverse and serious adverse events must be assessed by an investigator. The following are the minimum parameters to be collected for each event:

- Maximum intensity:
 - Mild is awareness of sign or symptom, but easily tolerated
 - Moderate is discomfort enough to interfere with usual activity
 - Severe is incapacitating with inability to work or do usual activity
 - Death
- Duration. The start and stop dates will be identified and recorded.
- Action taken in regards to the study drug. Does the event cause the study medication to be temporarily or permanently discontinued?
- Relationship to study medication. The investigator will determine if the study medication contributed to the AE/SAE. Factors to consider:
 - Exposure: Was participant exposed to the study medication?

Likely cause: Is the event reasonably explained by aetiology such as underlying disease or other environmental factors?

Re-challenge: Was the participant re-exposed to the study medication? If yes, did the event recur or worsen?

Consistency with the study medication: Is the clinical/pathology presentation of the event consistent with previous knowledge regarding the study medication?

- Details of any treatment given.

Expectedness of SAEs

SAEs must also be assessed for expectedness in this clinical setting. The investigator is responsible for determining whether an SAE is expected or not based on the underlying pregnancy and CS delivery, the pre-existing condition of the fetus/neonate, and the published reference safety information for betamethasone (including this protocol and the summary of product characteristics, such as the MedSafe Data Sheet). An unexpected adverse event/reaction is one that is not reported in the reference safety information, is more severe than previously reported or is not reasonably explained by the underlying condition.

Review of all of the known information about the SAE should conclude one of the following:

Expected Events:

- Expected Unrelated Event: the SAE is expected based on the known information about the study drug or the underlying condition and is not considered to be related to the study drug. This is referred to as an Expected SAE.
- Expected Related Event: an SAE which the Investigator considers possibly, probably or definitely related to the study drug. This is referred to as a SAR – Serious Adverse Reaction.

Unexpected Events:

- Unexpected Unrelated Event: the SAE is unexpected based on the known information about the drug or the underlying condition and is not considered related to the study drug. This is referred to as an Unexpected SAE.
- Unexpected Related Event: the SAE is unexpected based on the known information about the drug or the underlying condition and is considered possibly, probably or definitely related to the study drug. This is referred to as a SUSAR – Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction.

Fetal or neonatal death and maternal death and maternal life-threatening complications should always be considered unexpected events in this population and require immediate reporting.

13.4 Procedure for AE and SAE Reporting

All AEs and SAEs must be documented in the participant's CRF. SAEs may also require immediate reporting by the site, as below:

Actions for SAEs:

1. Report immediately, within 24 hours of becoming aware of the event:
 - SAR – suspected adverse reaction.
 - Unexpected SAE.
 - SUSAR – Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction.
2. Documented in the CRF only (do not require immediate reporting):
 - Expected SAE.

Unexpected SAEs, SUSARs and SARs will be reported to the C*STEROID DMC, regulatory authorities and ethics committees, as required.

13.5 Data and Safety Monitoring

A Safety Monitoring Committee (SMC) will be established to review all serious adverse events. The SMC will report back to the Trial Steering Committee (TSC). The TSC will report any safety issues to an independent Data Monitoring Committee (DMC). The C*STEROID DMC will be established using HRC DMC terms of reference and will include a senior obstetrician, senior neonatologist and a biostatistician. The DMC will review trial safety, efficacy and conduct and report to the TSC.

14. CONFIDENTIALITY & DATA MANAGEMENT

14.1 Confidentiality

Data will be collected on CRFs using the participant's study ID number to ensure confidentiality for each woman and child. Data will be entered onto hard copy CRFs and/or into an electronic eCRF database. Electronic databases will be stored on secure servers and access will be controlled by unique user ID and password, with full electronic tracking log. Completed hard copy CRFs will be submitted to the Auckland coordinating centre.

A copy of the signed consent form and contact details, including identifying information, for each randomised participant will be securely transmitted to the Auckland coordinating centre for the purpose of follow up. This data along with hard copy CRFs will be stored in the Liggins Institute, The University of Auckland for a minimum of 10 years (maternal) and for a minimum of 10 years after the age of majority (child). Study reports will contain only summary data. Identifiable data will not be reported or released to any third party.

All investigators, clinicians and participants will remain blinded to treatment allocations throughout the study. It is planned that data from the C*STEROID Feasibility Study will contribute to the C*STEROID Trial (once funded) and therefore investigators, clinicians and participants will remain blinded to treatment allocations until the full trial is complete and database lock has occurred. If the main trial is not funded within a reasonable timeframe, analyses of outcomes will occur by treatment group with first analyses by unrevealed treatment group. If a participant is un-blinded due to an urgent clinical need to reveal the study allocation the investigator is advised to limit the distribution of this information to other site staff or study personnel.

14.2 Access to Data and Data Sharing

The Trial Steering Committee will have access to the full dataset and oversee analysis, interpretation and reporting of results. The data that support the findings of this study will be made available in a public repository following publication of the full C*STEROID Trial.

15. OUTCOME MEASURES

15.1 Primary Outcome

Trial recruitment rate: number of participants recruited/number of individuals identified as eligible.

15.2 Secondary Outcomes

- the recruitment rate by gestational age, indication for delivery and recruiting site groups.
- the duration of follow-up that participants are willing to agree to.
- the type of follow-up that participants are willing to agree to.
- the reasons why women may decline to participate in such a trial.
- the barriers and enablers to trial participation by participant.
- the barriers and enablers to trial participation by research staff, medical professional and recruiting site status.
- the proportion of babies who complete serial measurements of neonatal pre-feed blood glucose concentrations as per protocol.
- The incidence of respiratory distress requiring >60 minutes of respiratory support. Including mechanical and non-invasive ventilation where sum of both is >60 minutes (e.g. intermittent positive pressure via endotracheal tube, nasal continuous positive airway pressure, Hi- or Lo-flow oxygen/air mix or increased ambient oxygen delivered into an incubator).
- the incidence of hypoglycaemia (blood glucose level <2.6 mmol/L) prior to primary hospital discharge.

15.3 C*STEROID Trial Outcome

Data from the C*STEROID Feasibility Study will contribute to the C*STEROID Trial outcomes:

Co-Primary outcome (benefit): incidence of respiratory distress requiring >60 mins respiratory support, including mechanical and non-invasive ventilation where sum of both is >60 minutes (e.g. intermittent positive pressure via endotracheal tube, nasal continuous positive airway pressure, Hi- or Lo-flow oxygen/air mix or increased ambient oxygen delivered into an incubator).

Co-Primary (harm): incidence of hypoglycaemia (blood glucose <2.6 mmol/L) prior to primary hospital discharge.

Secondary outcomes:

- NNU admission; duration of NNU stay; duration of hospital stay (to primary hospital discharge).
- Duration of respiratory support (sum of mechanical and non-invasive); severe respiratory distress defined as any mechanical ventilation and/or need for surfactant therapy; moderate respiratory distress defined as respiratory support (sum of mechanical and non-invasive) for >24 hours.
- Severe hypoglycaemia defined as blood glucose level <1.2 mmol/L.
- Early onset infection and/or late onset infection as defined by ANZNN.²⁷
- Maternal self-reported adverse effects of injections including gastrointestinal upset, insomnia, pain at injection site, bruising at injection site, infection at injection site.
- Maternal perinatal infectious morbidity requiring postpartum antibiotic therapy.
- Duration of maternal postnatal stay (to primary hospital discharge).
- Breastfeeding (exclusive and full) at six weeks postpartum.
- Maternal wellbeing and psychological status measured at baseline and six weeks postpartum.

16. STATISTICAL ANALYSES

We will review the feasibility study at six and 12 months after commencing recruitment. All data will be analysed as a single group, not by study treatment group. Descriptive statistics will be used for demographic and other baseline data. Recruitment rates will be calculated by number of participants recruited/number of individuals identified as eligible. This will be reported for the whole study population and by groups – gestational age (35⁺⁰-36⁺⁶, 37⁺⁰-38⁺⁶, 39⁺⁰-39⁺⁹ weeks), indication for CS (previous CS; maternal e.g. diabetes, preeclampsia; fetal e.g. SGA, fetal anomaly; multiple pregnancy; placental e.g. placenta praevia; maternal request; other) and by recruiting site (Auckland City Hospital and Tauranga).

Descriptive summary statistics will be used for all secondary outcomes.

17. STUDY TIMELINE

2018 - 2019

Protocol preparation

Central ethics application

Site engagement/local governance

Development of web-based data collection system & randomisation service

Manufacture and packaging of drug and placebo

2019

Recruitment to the C*STEROID Feasibility Study

2019 – 2020

Analysis of the C*STEROID Feasibility Study

2023

Contribution to the C*STEROID Trial (pending funding)

C*STEROID Trial data analysis and results publication

Children will be invited to participate in the later childhood outcome study at 6-7 years of age from 2025 (pending funding)

18. ETHICS & REGULATORY

The trial will be conducted in line with the Principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (1996) and the Note for Guidance on Good Clinical Practice (CPMP/ICH/135/95) issued by the European Medicines Agency, which is based on the International Committee for Harmonisation document E6, as well as any addendum or amendment to these guidelines which are implemented in the region where the trial is being carried out.

This trial is approved by the Southern Health and Disability Ethics Committee NZ (18/STH/227). All participating sites will have received ethics approval by an Institutional Review Board or Ethics Committee, local hospital governance approval and regulatory approval (if applicable) before commencing recruitment.

19. FUNDING

The Feasibility study is funded by a University of Auckland FRDF Liggins New Staff grant, the Hugo Charitable Trust, Cure Kids and Lottery Health Research New Zealand.

An application for funding has been made to the Health Research Council of New Zealand for the main C*STEROID Trial.

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APPENDIX

Algorithm for the monitoring and management of hypoglycaemia for C*STEROID infants.

This algorithm has been prepared using:

ADHB guideline for the management of hypoglycaemia

<https://www.starship.org.nz/for-health-professionals/newborn-services-clinical-guidelines/h/hypoglycaemia-in-the-neonate/>

Oral Dextrose Gel to treat Neonatal Hypoglycaemia: Clinical Practice Guidelines

https://www.fmhs.auckland.ac.nz/assets/fmhs/som/paed/docs/Oral_dextrose%20gel_%20guideline2.pdf

*For infants that meet criteria for routine BGC testing, e.g. small for gestational age, large for gestational age, preterm, the C*STEROID algorithm can be applied, however, BGC testing should be done 3 hourly and it is recommended that the neonatal/paediatric service should be notified if BGC is < 2.0mM at any stage. For infants receiving BGC testing for C*STEROID only it is appropriate to BGC at 3-4 hourly intervals.